

Revisiting the History of Sindh's Forts: A Comparative Study of Rani Kot, Kacha Qilla, and Pakka Qila with a Reinterpretation of Nerun Kot

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Abstract

This study re-evaluates the historical identification of Nerun Kot, traditionally associated with Hyderabad, by conducting a comparative architectural and historical analysis of three key forts in Sindh: Rani Kot, Kacha Qilla, and Pakka Qila. Combining onsite fieldwork, satellite imagery, and archival research, the paper examines construction materials, fortification patterns, citadel layouts, and water management systems to test the hypothesis that Rani Kot corresponds to the historic Nerun Kot. Field observations reveal that Rani Kot's massive stone walls bonded with gypsum paste, 64 bastions of mixed designs, integrated citadels, and a perennial freshwater spring sharply contrast with the smaller, mud or brick built Kacha Qilla and Pakka Qila, which lack natural water sources and extensive fortification systems. Historical texts—including Chach Nama (Fatahnama-e-Sindh), and Tarekh-e-Mazhar Shah Jahani further corroborate this evidence, consistently placing Nerun Kot in the Kirthar mountain range near Sewhan and describing features identical to those of Rani Kot. By synthesizing architectural and textual data, this study challenges the prevailing consensus and concludes that Nerun Kot was not Hyderabad but Rani Kot. Beyond clarifying a contested historical attribution, the research demonstrates the value of integrating field based and archival methods to refine understandings of Sindh's heritage and fortification history.

Keywords: Rani Kot Fort; Nerun Kot; Kacha Qilla; Pakka Qila; Sindh heritage

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INTRODUCTION

Recent archaeological research across the world has increasingly emphasized the study of fortifications to understand political authority, landscape use, and regional power dynamics. Advances in methods such as remote sensing, geophysical prospection, and landscape archaeology have significantly reshaped interpretations of ancient defensive systems. In Europe, interdisciplinary analyses combining architectural study, topographic modelling, and environmental data have deepened understanding of medieval fortification strategies and settlement hierarchies (Creighton, 2002). Large-scale LiDAR-based investigations in Southeast Asia have uncovered extensive fortified and hydraulic networks previously invisible beneath dense vegetation, fundamentally altering interpretations of socio-political organization (Evans et al., 2013). Remote sensing-driven research in Eurasia and the Middle East has likewise mapped widespread fortification systems, demonstrating the antiquity and spatial diversity of defensive landscapes across arid and steppe regions (Casana, 2021). Comparative work on Roman frontier forts has shown how variations in fort design reflect changing administrative and military priorities across diverse ecological zones (Witcher, 2008).

Meanwhile, archaeological studies in the Arabian Peninsula have highlighted how fortified settlements functioned as key nodes linking pastoralist mobility, resource control, and urban development (Magee, 2014). Collectively, these global developments underscore the value of integrating architectural, environmental, and archival evidence, an approach directly relevant to re-examining Sindh's historic fortifications. Forts have long served as focal points of political authority, military strategy, and regional identity in Sindh's history (R. Suresh, 2021). Among them, Rani Kot, Kacha Qilla, and Pakka Qila occupy a prominent place in the architectural and historical landscape of southern Pakistan (Figure 1). Traditionally, the historic Nerun Kot has been associated with Hyderabad (Shaikh Abdul Mateen Umri, 1657, Sindhi Adabi Board, 2006, Ishtiaq Ansari, 2022); however, discrepancies in geographic descriptions and structural features in historical sources raise questions about this attribution. Revisiting this assumption offers an opportunity to clarify Sindh's early medieval geography and to reassess the strategic importance of its fortifications.

Fig. 1. Study Area indicating Rani Kot, Kacha Qilla, and Pakka Qilla.

The three forts under study differ markedly in their construction materials, defensive layouts, and geographic settings. Rani Kot, the largest fortification in the region, stands in the Kirthar mountain range and features massive stone walls, integrated citadels, and a perennial spring (UNESCO, 1993). By contrast, Kacha Qilla and Pakka Qila, located in Hyderabad (Heritage of Sindh, 2019), are built primarily of mud and brick and lack both the scale and natural water resources observed at Rani Kot. These distinctions mirror the descriptions in historical chronicles such as *Chach Nama* (Fatahnama-e-Sindh) (Makhdoom Ameer Ahmed, 2020) and *Tarekh-e-Mazhar Shah Jahani* (Sindhi Adabi Board, 1994), which locate Nerun Kot in mountainous terrain nearby Sewhan and describe features consistent with Rani Kot rather than Hyderabad's forts. This paper aims to test the hypothesis that Rani Kot, rather than Hyderabad, corresponds to the historic Nerun Kot. To achieve this, the study employs a comparative analysis of architecture, fortification patterns, and water management systems, combined with a critical reading of primary and secondary historical sources. Through this interdisciplinary approach, the research not only reassesses the identity of Nerun Kot but also highlights the broader significance of integrating field based architectural surveys with archival evidence to refine historical understanding of Sindh's heritage.

METHODOLOGY

This research adopted a comparative analysis approach to examine Rani Kot, Kacha Qilla, and Pakka Qila, focusing on their architecture, infrastructure, and historical significance. The methodology was designed to generate both empirical (on site) and textual (archival) evidence to support the hypothesis that Rani Kot, rather than Hyderabad, corresponds to the historic Nerun Kot. The study compared the three forts across multiple dimensions, including size, structure, defensive features, materials, and water management systems, to highlight similarities and differences in their design, usage, and strategic importance. Primary sources of data collection included direct field observations, photographic documentation, on-site measurements, and notes recorded during visits to the three forts, as well as original historical materials such as early maps, chronicles, and archival manuscripts. These primary datasets provided first-hand evidence regarding architectural features, construction materials, topographical context, and historical references to Nerun Kot, enabling the study to ground its comparative analysis in authentic, verifiable information drawn from both physical sites and historical records.

Field visits were conducted to Rani Kot, Kacha Qilla, and Pakka Qila to collect primary data. During these visits, photographs of architectural features, fortification patterns, and construction materials were taken, while detailed notes were recorded on the current state of preservation, layout, and the location of each fort relative to nearby geographic features. Particular attention was paid to Rani Kot's perennial fresh water spring to document its uniqueness in comparison with the other two forts. In addition to onsite visits, current maps and satellite imagery, particularly from Google Earth, were used to measure and visualize fort layouts, boundaries, and their broader geographic contexts. Historical maps of Sindh were also examined to trace the shifting identification of Nerun Kot and to understand the forts' connections to old trade routes, rivers, and settlements. The architectural and material analysis involved detailed observation of construction techniques, materials (stone, mud, lime, and bricks), and fortification patterns such as walls, bastions, gates, and citadels. Observed materials were correlated with descriptions in historical texts to confirm authenticity and contextual accuracy.

To complement and contextualize on-site findings, the study drew upon a wide range of historical and archival sources, including primary and secondary texts such as Chach Nama, Tarekh-e-Mazhar Shah Jahani, Aina-e-Qadeem Sindh, and Badar Abro's works on Sindh's heritage, as well as relevant travelogues and maps. This archival research specifically focused on clarifying the identity of Nerun Kot and tracing historical narratives surrounding Rani Kot. The comparative framework evaluated the forts on several key aspects, including size and layout (overall dimensions, fortification perimeters, and internal organization), structural features (bastions, gates, defensive walls, and citadels), materials used (types and durability of construction materials), defensive features (strategic location, elevation, and natural defenses), and water management (availability and sustainability of water resources, with special emphasis on Rani Kot's year round spring). Data from onsite visits, maps, and historical texts were synthesized to create comparative tables and visual maps. This evidence was then used to test the central hypothesis that Rani Kot, not Hyderabad, represents the historic Nerun Kot.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Architectural Features

Rani Kot

Field observations indicate that all walls, bastions, and residential structures of Rani Kot are constructed from exceptionally strong stone (Figure 2a), bonded with gypsum paste to create highly durable fortifications. This material choice distinguishes Rani Kot as the largest and strongest of the three forts. Rock carvings were documented in the inner fort known as Meeri Kot (Figure 3), suggesting either symbolic or functional inscriptions that warrant further study. A total of 64 bastions were identified, displaying a variety of forms, round, square, and rectangular, indicating a mixed defensive design. Four gates, oriented in different directions (Figure 4), provide access to the fort, strategically positioned to align with historic trade routes and defensive approaches.

Fig. 2. Material composition of three forts, (a) Rani Kot, (b) Kacha Qilla, and (c) Pakka Qilla.

Kacha Qilla

Kacha Qilla was originally constructed with mud bricks (Figure 2b) bound with mud mortar, typical of early, less-permanent fortification techniques. Later additions, notably shrines built from red bricks (Figure 5), reflect post-original constructions unrelated to the fort's initial defensive purpose. No evidence of rock carvings or stone-built features was observed. Historical remains reveal the prior existence of four round bastions, now largely demolished but detectable through

aerial or drone surveys (Figure 6). Only two gates; One is main gate for entry and exit points and another is the secrete gate (Figure 7).

Pakka Qilla

Pakka Qilla was originally built from red bricks bonded with mortar (Figure 2c). Over time, significant alterations occurred, and modern residential structures have been incorporated within its walls. No rock carvings or stone construction were documented. Three bastions, mainly round in shape, were observed, although several have suffered damage (Figure 8). The fort currently has one main gate functioning as the principal entrance and exit and one secrete gate (Figure 9).

Fig. 3. Rock carvings in Meeri Kot.

Fig. 4. Topographical map of Rani Kot. Blue line indicating Natural Water Spring, Red dots are indicating the bastions, four gates shown with the location icons, and three citadels are presented in yellow colour.

Fig. 7. Gates of Kacha Qilla, (a) Main Gate, and (b) Secret Gate.

Fig. 8. Original Map of Pakka Qilla, bottom side indicating the remains of bastions.

Fig. 9. Gates of Pakka Qilla, (a) Main Gate, and (b) Secret Gate.

Fortification Patterns

Rani Kot

The fortifications of Rani Kot reveal a massive perimeter design with wall thicknesses ranging from 2 to 12 feet and heights between 6 and 18 feet (Figure 10a). Constructed of limestone and gypsum paste (Figure 10b), the walls follow a zigzag pattern, creating stronger defensive angles (Figure 11). Although only a single wall layer exists, its width is sufficient for carts and horses to traverse along the top. Sixty-four bastions, round, rectangular, and square, are strategically positioned along the perimeter. Four gates, facing major trade routes and likely enemy approaches, provide controlled access. Internally, the fort contains three citadels: Meeri Kot (residential), Sher Ghar, and Mohan Kot (military sections). The fort is integrated with the Kirthar mountain range, using natural hills to enhance defense. Two wells, two reservoirs (one inside, one outside), and a perennial freshwater spring within the fort highlight a sophisticated water management system that would sustain inhabitants during siege conditions (Figure 4).

Fig. 10. Walls of Rani Kot fort, (a) Thickness of fort wall, and (b) limestone and gypsum paste used to construct the fort.

Fig. 11. Zigzag-patterned wall of Rani Kot.

Kacha Qilla

Kacha Qilla's perimeter walls, composed of clay bricks and mud mortar, measure 3 to 5 feet in thickness and 8 to 15 feet in height. The walls form a triangular pattern and are built as a single layer. Nine bastions, now mostly reduced to remains, were originally half-rounded in shape (Figure 6). Only two gates exist, oriented toward residential areas and historic routes (Figure 7). Unlike Rani Kot, Kacha Qilla lacks internal citadels or specialized sections. Built on a hillock, the fort appears to rely on elevation rather than massive construction for defense. No wells, reservoirs, or springs were identified, suggesting limited water security.

Pakka Qilla

Pakka Qilla's walls, constructed from red bricks and mortar, range from 3 to 5 feet in thickness and rise dramatically to heights of 20 to 50 feet. The walls form a rectangular perimeter and are single layered. Eight rounded bastions are placed at intervals along the fort walls (Figure 8). Two gates (a main gate and a secondary secret gate) provide entry, oriented toward residential and defensive routes (Figure 9). Like Kacha Qilla, Pakka Qilla contains no internal citadels and is situated on a hillock to gain natural defensive advantage. While reservoirs once existed, they are now demolished, and no springs or wells were observed.

Comparative Discussion

The findings show a clear gradient in construction quality and defensive sophistication among the three forts (Figure 2). Rani Kot stands out with its massive stone construction, diverse bastion designs, multiple citadels, and integrated water management system, features consistent with a large military and administrative complex (Figure 4). In contrast, Kacha Qilla and Pakka Qilla exhibit lighter construction using mud or brick, fewer bastions, and limited water facilities, suggesting they served more localized or administrative functions. The zigzagging walls of Rani Kot (Figure 11) and its year-round spring also indicate advanced strategic planning absent in the other two forts. These architectural and fortification distinctions (Table 1) support the argument that Rani Kot occupied a more significant and enduring role in Sindh's history than Kacha Qilla or Pakka Qilla. The presence of citadels, strategic water sources, and integration with natural hills aligns with descriptions historically attributed to Nerun Kot, lending weight to the hypothesis that Rani Kot rather than Hyderabad may represent the true location of Nerun Kot.

Table 1

Comparison of the features of three forts.

Feature	Rani Kot	Kacha Qilla	Pakka Qilla
Construction Material	Stone walls bonded with gypsum paste; extremely durable	Mud bricks bonded with mud mortar; later shrines of red brick	Red bricks bonded with mortar; later modern houses inside
Rock Carvings	Present (Meeri Kot)	Absent	Absent
Bastions	64 (round, square, rectangular)	9 (originally half-round, mostly demolished)	8 (rounded, some damaged)
Number of Gates	4 gates (different directions)	2 gates	2 gates (one main, one secret/emergency)
Internal Citadels	3 (Meeri Kot – residential; Sher Ghar & Mohan Kot – military)	None	None

Wall Thickness (feet)	2–12	3–5	3–5
Wall Height (feet)	6–18	8–15	20–50
Wall Shape	Zigzag	Triangular	Rectangular
Layers of Walls	Single but wide enough for carts/horses	Single	Single
Natural Defensive Use	Integrated with Kirthar mountain range	Built on hillock	Built on hillock
Water Management	2 wells, 2 reservoirs (inside & outside), perennial spring inside fort	No wells, reservoirs, or springs	Reservoirs existed but demolished; no wells or springs
Strategic Orientation of Gates	Facing trade routes and defensive approaches	Facing residence and historic routes	Facing residence and historic routes
Current State	Well-preserved structure with clear fortification features	Mostly ruins with later constructions (shrines)	Partially intact; modern residences inside

Historical and Archival Research

To contextualize the on-site findings and architectural comparisons, this study engaged in extensive historical and archival research. Primary and secondary texts, including *Chach Nama (Fatahnama-e-Sindh)* (Makhdoom Ameer Ahmed, 2020), and *Tarekh-e-Mazhar Shah Jahani (Sindhi Adabi Board, 1994)*, were systematically examined. In addition, relevant travelogues and historical maps were reviewed to clarify the identity of Nerun Kot and to trace historical narratives related to Rani Kot.

Evidence from Chach Nama (Fatahnama-e-Sindh)

The *Chach Nama* (Makhdoom Ameer Ahmed, 2020), provides vivid descriptions of Nerun Kot that strongly correlate with features observed at Rani Kot:

Page 217, Lines 10–11: “*We are at the Nerun Kot, in which there is a water spring of which the water is as clear as the eyes of a lover; it also has the grassing area which is more pleasant than Bhaag-e-Iram.*”

Page 219, Lines 6–7: “*We are in a fort that is superior to Alexander’s stone-made wall.*”

These descriptions mirror the actual infrastructure of Rani Kot, which uniquely contains a perennial freshwater spring and is built of massive stone walls (Figure 12). By contrast, neither Kacha Qilla nor Pakka Qilla has any spring or stone fortification comparable to Alexander’s wall. This comparison strongly suggests that Nerun Kot cannot be Hyderabad (or its forts) but corresponds instead to Rani Kot.

Fig. 12. Chach Nama (Fatahnama-e-Sindh), (a) Cover page, (b) Page 217, and (c) Page 219.

Evidence from Tarekh-e-Mazhar Shah Jahani

Tarekh-e-Mazhar Shah Jahani (originally published in 1635; translated and published by the Sindhi Adabi Board, 2nd Edition, 1994) provides geographical details about the location of Nerun Kot:

Page 23 & 31, Lines 8–10: “Nerun Kot Fort is located in the Kirthar mountain ranges, specifically on the Lundi hillocks, straight from Sewhan”.

Page 281, Lines 4 & 16: “Neerun Kot is 25 Koh away from Sewhan Fort.”

Koh is an indigenous Sindhi unit of distance historically used to measure travel between locations. One Koh is approximately 2 km. Based on this, the distance between Sewhan and Rani Kot today is about 88 km, whereas Kacha Qilla and Pakka Qilla are approximately 146 km away. These descriptions align with the topography of Rani Kot, which lies within the Khirthar mountain range and is geographically in line with Sewhan (Figure 13). In contrast, Kacha Qilla and Pakka Qilla are neither situated within the Kirthar range nor aligned directly with Sewhan.

Fig. 13. Tarekh-e-Mazhar Shah Jahani, (a) Cover Page, (b) Page 23, (c) Page 31, and (d) Page 281.

Synthesis of Historical Evidence

When combined with architectural and fortification evidence, these textual references collectively reinforce the argument that Nerun Kot was not Hyderabad but rather Rani Kot. The presence of a perennial spring, stone fortifications described as “superior to “The Wall of Alexander” Alexander’s wall,” and its confirmed location in the Kirthar mountains all converge to support this conclusion. This interpretation challenges the prevailing historical consensus and emphasizes the importance of integrating field based architectural research with critical readings of primary historical sources.

CONCLUSION

This study set out to re-evaluate the long-standing assumption that the historic Nerun Kot referenced in early Sindhi chronicles corresponds to the present-day city of Hyderabad. Through a systematic comparative analysis integrating architectural field surveys, structural documentation, landscape assessment, and archival research, the findings presented here offer a compelling alternative interpretation. The evidence demonstrates that Rani Kot differs fundamentally from Kacha Qilla and Pakka Qilla not only in scale and materiality but also in strategic planning, hydrological integration, and geographic placement. Its monumental stone walls, multi-tiered defensive system, subsidiary citadels, and perennial freshwater spring constitute a fortification complex of a magnitude and sophistication not paralleled in the Hyderabad forts.

When these architectural and environmental characteristics are correlated with textual descriptions in Chach Nama (Fatahnama-e-Sindh) and Tarekh-e-Mazhar Shah Jahani, strong similarity emerges. Both chronicles situate Nerun Kot within hilly terrain near Sewhan and describe defensive features and internal water resources absent in the Hyderabad forts but clearly present at Rani Kot. Conversely, Kacha Qilla and Pakka Qilla, constructed primarily of mud and brick, lacking integrated water systems, and located in the plains rather than the Kirthar mountains, align poorly with early historical accounts. These discrepancies underscore that the traditional identification of Nerun Kot with Hyderabad is based more on later historiographical convention than on architectural or textual evidence.

By synthesizing on-site measurements with a critical reading of primary sources, this research provides robust grounds for reinterpreting the historical geography of Sindh. The conclusion that Rani Kot is the more accurate candidate for the ancient Nerun Kot challenges entrenched narratives and invites a re-mapping of early medieval political centers in the region. This reframing has broader implications for understanding Sindh’s patterns of settlement, defense, and regional authority. More broadly, the study highlights the value of integrated, multidisciplinary methodologies in archaeological and historical research. The convergence of architectural fieldwork, landscape analysis, and close textual examination shows how combining empirical and documentary evidence can illuminate ambiguities that neither approach could resolve independently. Such an approach offers a powerful framework for reassessing other contested historical identifications across South Asia.

Ultimately, this investigation contributes not only to the scholarship on Sindh's fortifications but also to the wider discourse on how historical narratives are constructed, perpetuated, and corrected. By demonstrating that longstanding assumptions can, and should, be revisited through rigorous, evidence-driven inquiry, the study underscores the importance of continuously re-engaging with the material and textual heritage that shapes our understanding of the past.

Competing Interests

The authors declared no known competing interests.

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